

Guidelines for Poster Submission

The selected posters will be displayed on the Conference webpage and at the Conference Social Media Platforms during the poster session and at least 200 days after the Conference Ending. During all our previous conferences, the poster session was a great success and called the attention of many interested people. It is a fantastic opportunity to discuss your work with high level scientists and to have a substantial impact on policy-makers.

Please note that, due to strict **Scientiae Naturalis** communication regulations, all posters will need to go through the **Scientiae Naturalis** communication division for clearance before being uploaded on the official website.

For this reason, you are kindly requested to:

- ✚ Design your poster using the PowerPoint template for an A0 size.
- ✚ Poster sections: In almost all scientific posters you will find a title, author names and affiliations, introduction, methods, results, conclusions, and acknowledgements sections. Some other additions you might wish to include is a references section, for example. You also should add your **ORCID number**
- ✚ Please use the following specifications:
 - Titles - Verdana, size 80; Headings/subtitle - Verdana, size 45; Body text - Georgia, font size 32; Caption – Verdana, font size 22;
 - Participants may submit any entries which include content generated by any generative **Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool**, including but not limited to photorealistic imagery, graphics or other artistic media.
 - Participants are allowed to use AI technology for ideation or editing purposes. Whenever a participant uses AI technology for these or any other purposes, they shall disclose how such technology was specifically used.
 - Should AI have been used in a way that is not compliant with these rules, **Scientiae Naturalis** reserves the right, in its sole discretion, to disqualify the entry from the competition.

